

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE STUDY OF HISTORICAL TOPICS IN ELEMENTARY READING CLASSES

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Abstract: The role of interactive methods in the study of historical topics in elementary reading classes. Interactive methods of teaching were thought about identifying problems, analyzing data, finding opportunities and measures to solve problems, developing specific goals, and being able to listen to the interlocutor.

Key words: Keywords: Interactive methods: "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blitz-inquiry", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Relationship", "Plan", "Interview", Strategies: Brainstorm, Boomerang, Gallery, Zigzag, Staircase, Mirror, Rotation, T-Table, Rounded Snow and Graphic Organizers: Fish Skeleton", "BBB", "Concept table", "Venn diagram", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?".

Interactive teaching methods require the ability to identify problems, analyze data, find opportunities and measures to solve problems, develop clear goals, listen to the interlocutor, and respond accordingly[1].

In recent years, great reforms have been carried out in our country in order to bring the education system in line with world standards in all respects. Our wise people said that education cannot be separated from education, and education cannot be separated from education. In the process of education, while imparting knowledge fulfills its task, upbringing also fulfills its task. Before, we limited ourselves to educating students in the spirit of following the rules, becoming polite, and doing good to others. However, it is very difficult for today's youth to start an independent life without having hygienic education, ecological culture, economic knowledge and legal literacy. That's why school teachers and educators, in addition to having a lot of knowledge, skills and qualifications, are required to use modern information and communication tools, to be aware of the latest youth and education news[2-3].

In order to increase the efficiency of the lesson and to form students as well-rounded individuals, lessons should be organized actively and meaningfully. To organize such lessons, interactive methods help the teacher in the course of the lesson. Through such methods, both the teacher and the learner are in action. Therefore, the efficiency of the lesson is high[4-5].

Today, the following most popular technologies are used in the organization of interactive education in educational institutions of the republic:

1. Interactive methods: "Case study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blitz survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Relationship", "Plan", "Conversation" and others.
2. Strategies: "Brainstorm", "Boomerang", "Gallery", "Zigzag", "Staircase", "Museum", "Rotation", "T-table", "Snowball" and many more there are types.
3. Graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Concept chart", "Venn diagram", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", "How?" and there are other types.

Interactivity - mutual activity, movement, affectiveness, occurs in student-teacher, student-student conversations. The main goal of interactive methods is to create an environment for the active, free, creative thinking of the student, to use his needs, interests, and internal capabilities by creating the most favorable environment and situation for the educational process. Such lessons are held in such a way that no student is left out, and they have the opportunity to clearly express what they have heard, read, and seen. A process of mutual exchange of ideas ensues. Pupils' enthusiasm and interest in learning increases, mutual friendly relations are formed. Interactive education, by its nature, includes heuristic (thinking, searching, finding) conversation through didactic games - creating and solving a problem situation by designing the lesson process, creative - creativity-based implementation methods using information and communication technologies[6].

Education on the basis of information and communication technologies, in turn, consists of teaching with the help of computer programs, distance learning, teaching on the basis of Internet networks, media - educational methods.

In primary education, methods based on the design of heuristic conversations through didactic games according to the age characteristics, literacy levels, and personal nature of students are widely used. It would ensure high quality and efficiency if during the teaching process every student worked on assignments at the level of his/her ability to master. This can only be achieved through differentiated education[7].

The study of historical topics also fully adheres to the educational principles and methods created by our current pedagogy. However, while studying these topics does not always require the use of activities such as working on vocabulary,

introductory conversation, creating a text plan, these types of activities are given a wide place in studying topics specific to past times[8].

Another method used in studying works on historical topics is students' work on vocabulary. Work on reading texts cannot be imagined without work on vocabulary. Because not all texts in the textbook are understandable for students. They do not understand some words, and even if they understand the words, they cannot use them in their speech. Determining the volume of words used in students' speech and increasing it as much as possible is the responsibility of all teachers teaching in primary classes. By the time a child reaches school, the average child will have some vocabulary. But in school life, this vocabulary is enriched by 20-30 words every day[9].

It is natural to encounter words that are difficult to understand in the texts on historical topics taken from primary school textbooks. Texts on historical topics in these classes increased relatively after the independence of our republic. This can be explained by the fact that we are studying more texts on this topic, and we are paying more attention to our spirituality and values. By the time children reach school, they will have a certain vocabulary. But in school life, this vocabulary is enriched. One of the ways to develop a child's vocabulary and speech is to ensure that he answers questions completely[10].

Community spirituality is of great importance in child upbringing and primary education. It is important to educate children on the basis of national values, in particular, the rich heritage left by the scholars of the East.

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